

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of some unsaturated acids by quinolinium bromochromate

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The oxidation of maleic, fumaric, crotonic and cinnamic acids by quinolinium bromochromate (QBC) in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding epoxide. The reaction is of first order with respect to QBC and the acid. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of these acids was studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect was analyzed by Kamlet's and Swain's multiparametric equations. Solvent effect indicated the importance of the cation-solvating power of the solvent. A mechanism involving a three-centre transition state has been postulated.

Pyridinium and quinolinium halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻⁵. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of the oxidation by halochromates, a chromium(VI) species, and several reports have already been emanated from our laboratory⁶⁻⁹, but there seems to be no report on the oxidation of alkenes by quinolinium bromochromate (QBC). We have, therefore, undertaken an investigation of the oxidation of fumaric acid (FA), maleic acid (MA), crotonic acid (CrA) and cinnamic acid (CiA) by QBC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as a solvent. Mechanistic aspects are discussed.

Results and discussion

The final product, in the oxidation of crotonic, cinnamic, maleic/fumaric acids is acetone, acetophenone and pyruvic acid respectively. These must have arisen from the corresponding epoxides by rearrangement and decarboxylation as shown in equation (1),

(R = Ph, Me or COOH)

Epoxies are known to rearrange to ketones¹⁰. β -Ketoacids readily decarboxylate in acidic solutions¹¹. Therefore, the overall oxidation process may be written as follows,

QBC undergoes a two-electron change. This is in accord with our earlier observations with other halochromates⁶⁻⁹.

Rate laws :

The reactions are first order with respect to QBC. A plot of $\log [\text{QBC}]$ against time is linear (Fig. 1). Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants do not depend on the initial $[\text{QBC}]$. The reaction rate increases linearly with an in-

Fig. 1. A plot of $\log (a-x)$ against time for the oxidation of cinnamic acid by QBC.

crease in the concentration of the reductant (Table 1). The oxidation of acids in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1). The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 1). The hydrogen ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The values of a and b , for the oxidation of cinnamic acid are $16.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $62.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($r^2 = 0.9992$, $sd = 0.67$).

The rates of oxidation of the unsaturated acids were determined at four different temperatures and the activation

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of cinnamic acid by QBC at 298 K

10^3 [QBC] mol dm ⁻³	[CiA] mol dm ⁻³	[TsOH] mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{obs}$ s ⁻¹
1.00	0.10	0.00	17.1
1.00	0.20	0.00	33.4
1.00	0.40	0.00	67.2
1.00	0.60	0.00	101
1.00	0.80	0.00	134
1.00	1.00	0.00	165
2.00	0.20	0.00	34.1
4.00	0.20	0.00	32.6
6.00	0.20	0.00	33.8
8.00	0.20	0.00	33.1
1.00	0.10	0.10	22.7
1.00	0.10	0.20	28.8
1.00	0.10	0.40	41.1
1.00	0.10	0.60	55.2
1.00	0.10	0.80	66.1
1.00	0.10	1.00	78.9
1.00	0.40	0.00	67.6*

* Contained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of unsaturated acids by QBC

Subst.	$10^4 k_2 / (\text{dm}^{-3} \text{ mol s}^{-1})$				ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
FA	5.35	8.58	14.0	23.4	34.9 ± 0.8	-187 ± 3	90.4 ± 0.7
CrA	16.2	26.8	44.4	72.5	35.5 ± 0.4	-175 ± 1	87.6 ± 0.3
MA	20.8	32.4	52.8	82.6	32.7 ± 0.6	-183 ± 2	87.1 ± 0.5
CiA	108	165	261	378	29.6 ± 0.5	-180 ± 1	83.1 ± 0.4

parameters were calculated (Table 2).

The rates of the oxidation of the unsaturated acids were obtained in nineteen different organic solvents. The solubility of reagents and reaction of QBC with primary and secondary alcohols limited the choice of solvents. There was no reaction with the chosen solvents. Kinetics was similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 3.

The correlation of the rate constants, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (4) of Kamlet *et al.*¹² was not significant. It explained *ca.* 84% of the data.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (4)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the

Table 3. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of cinnamic acid by QBC at 298 K

Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Chloroform	66.1	Acetic acid	17.4
1,2-Dichloroethane	79.4	Cyclohexane	5.02
Dichloromethane	69.2	Toluene	26.9
DMSO	165	Acetophenone	89.1
Acetone	63.1	THF	38.0
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	109	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	33.8
Butanone	56.2	1,4-Dioxane	44.7
Nitrobenzene	75.8	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	22.9
Benzene	31.6	Carbon disulfide	13.5
Ethyl acetate	29.5		

hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation¹³ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also (5),

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (5)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of equation (5), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 0.50 (\pm 0.04) A + 1.36 (\pm 0.03) B - 3.40 \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9943; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.08$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.31 (\pm 0.45) A - 2.47 \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0273; sd = 0.36; n = 19; \psi = 1.01$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.32 (\pm 0.09) B - 3.24 \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9232; sd = 0.10; n = 19; \psi = 0.28$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.06 \pm 0.11 (A + B) - 3.37 \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8458; sd = 0.14; n = 19; \psi = 0.42$$

Here ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹⁴. The rates of oxidation of cinnamic acid in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation [cf. equation (5)] with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone accounts for *ca.* 92% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 85% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 85% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against

the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.4905$; $sd = 0.26$; $\psi = 0.73$).

Mechanism :

The observed acid-dependence of the reaction rate may be explained on the basis of a protonation of QBC in a pre-equilibrium (10), with both the protonated and deprotonated forms being active oxidizing species.

The reactions of alkenes with various Cr^{VI} derivatives have been widely studied. The most extensively studied derivative is chromyl chloride. The results of the present study are comparable with those obtained with chromyl chloride.

The low values of the enthalpies of activation indicate that bond-cleavage is not extensive in the formation of the activated complex. The formation of a rigid cyclic activated complex is indicated by the large negative values of the entropies of activation. The probable structures if the activated complex are **I**, **II**, **III** and **IV**. **III** is a kin to the activated complexes of concerted *cis*-1,3-cycloaddition reactions, which are characterized by values of reaction constants (ρ) close to zero¹⁵. Therefore, an activated complex of type **III** is unlikely in view of the fact that the reactions of substituted styrenes¹⁶ and alkenes¹⁷ exhibit moderately large negative reaction constants (-1.99 and -2.63 respectively).

In reactions involving fairly large degree of carbocationic character in the activated complex, reaction constant values of -3 to -5 have been observed^{18,19}. In the oxidation of *trans*-monosubstituted cinnamic acid by acid borate, Reddy and Sundaram²⁰ observed that electron-withdrawing groups have a little effect on the rate of oxidation while electron-donating groups have substantial effect on the reactivity. They obtained a reaction constant of -3.7 for the electron-donating groups. The activated complex is proposed to be a benzylic carbocation in character. Therefore, the reported value of *ca.* -2 in the oxidation of styrenes¹⁶ by chromyl chloride mitigates against an activated complex with a fully developed positive charge (**IV**). In the present reaction also, replacement of a methyl group by a phenyl group results in a modest rate enhancement (*ca.* 7 times).

A perusal of the relative rates of the oxidation (*cf.* Table 2) showed that maleic acid is oxidized at a rate *ca.* 3 times that of fumaric acid. This militates against the formation of the activated complex **II**. The formation of a four-membered cyclic activated complex is likely to be more vulnerable to steric factors. Sterically the attack of QBC on the open face of maleic acid (having two hydrogens) is more facile than on fumaric acid. Had the activated complex been a four-

membered cyclic structure, the difference in the rates of maleic and fumaric acids would have been much sharper. A formation of even the three-membered cyclic activated complex (**I**) is less hindered in the oxidation of the *cis*-acid as compared to that in the *trans*-acid. However, the data against an involvement of the activated complex **II** is not conclusive. Freeman *et al.*^{16,17,21} also have not been able to show conclusively whether the activated complex had a three- or a four-member cyclic structure.

The analysis of the solvent effect also supports the proposed mechanism. The fact that the reaction proceeds faster in more polar solvents is in accordance with the formation of a partially charged activated complex from two neutral molecules. The relatively major contribution of the cation-solvating power of the solvents supports the generation of an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state. Further, the relatively low magnitude of the regression coefficient, b , is consistent with the development of a partial positive charge in the activated complex. In the oxidation of benzaldehyde by pyridinium fluorochromate⁶, where the formation of a carbocationic activated complex has been postulated, the value of b is 1.73. To conclude, though both structures **I** and **II** are possible for the activated complex, the balance of evidence is in favour of **I**.

Experimental

Materials :

The unsaturated acids were commercial products and were used as obtained. QBC was prepared by the reported method⁵ and its purity was ascertained by an iodometric method. Solvents were purified by the usual methods²². Due to non-aqueous nature of the medium, toluene-*p*-sulfonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions.

Product analysis :

Product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions i.e. with an excess of the reductant over QBC. In a typical experiment, the unsaturated acid (0.2 mol) and QBC (6.18 g, 0.02 mol) were dissolved in 100 ml of DMSO and was allowed to stand for *ca.* 12 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 cm³) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol, and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 2.52 g (88%) and 2.26 g (79%) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP of acetophenone, acetone and pyruvic acid in the oxidation of cinnamic, crotonic and maleic/fumaric acids respectively. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method, was 3.95 ± 0.06 .

Kinetic measurements :

The pseudo-first order conditions, were attained by keeping an excess ($\times 10$ or greater) of the reductant over QBC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed at constant temperature (± 0.1 K). The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of QBC spectrophotometrically at 356 nm for at least three half-lives. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r^2 > 0.995$) plots of $\log [\text{QBC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs indicated that the rate constants are reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was evaluated from the relation: $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{reductant}]$. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH.

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